

Circle packing inside a regular hexagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 400$ congruent disks packed inside a regular hexagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular hexagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 400$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular hexagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 400$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 400$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceeded by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.464101615138	0.520899741121	41	0.126161767649	0.789109684719
3	0.433012701892	0.680174761588	42	0.125108623258	0.794916966655
4	0.375015221341	0.680229979624	43	0.124815220497	0.8100308111
5	0.333404971008	0.672066320823	44	0.123304899729	0.808930725545
6	0.316987298108	0.729009112318	45	0.121261865975	0.800127125304
7	0.316987298108	0.850510631038	46	0.120631837547	0.809430760397
8	0.269585370786	0.703040939766	47	0.120345617062	0.823107199494
9	0.249261972966	0.676164790379	48	0.120345617062	0.840620118632
10	0.24275632254	0.712588953983	49	0.116441613111	0.803360534217
11	0.232050807569	0.716237144042	50	0.115694712596	0.809272930291
12	0.232050807569	0.781349611682	51	0.115386056418	0.821059865157
13	0.216506350946	0.73685599172	52	0.115386056418	0.837159078199
14	0.214290684433	0.777378644489	53	0.112253527371	0.807558233841
15	0.201559210543	0.73687622202	54	0.111600904574	0.813255811881
16	0.200025787346	0.774087306712	55	0.111119358912	0.82118334024
17	0.194813312769	0.780160882191	56	0.111119069712	0.836109594294
18	0.193997690565	0.819150331291	57	0.109704794905	0.829514652236
19	0.193997690565	0.864658683029	58	0.109491615458	0.840790327271
20	0.176152871147	0.750425242745	59	0.109239712177	0.85135578675
21	0.175149750125	0.778997968601	60	0.109233502047	0.865687111165
22	0.168017815756	0.750985127277	61	0.109233502047	0.880115229684
23	0.166338331558	0.769503331353	62	0.104279435263	0.815242884313
24	0.163462238508	0.775432701309	63	0.103572509148	0.817198443781
25	0.159724477011	0.771224725334	64	0.102993330016	0.820911161393
26	0.158493649054	0.789759871678	65	0.102992974872	0.833732148467
27	0.158493649054	0.820135251358	66	0.100973952318	0.81369310004
28	0.151660010858	0.778750221348	67	0.10051180591	0.818477869441
29	0.150002435355	0.789028343675	68	0.0999271941382	0.821058846924
30	0.150002435355	0.816236217595	69	0.0998817061449	0.83237491095
31	0.144498618555	0.782685107531	70	0.0989535783749	0.828817732109
32	0.142897923161	0.790132268449	71	0.0977269521851	0.819945608573
33	0.142870299182	0.814508900714	72	0.0974584665872	0.826931680606
34	0.140313381692	0.80942215357	73	0.0970835183556	0.831978034483
35	0.13982776274	0.827471126375	74	0.0969988452825	0.84190450716
36	0.139768253701	0.850388865364	75	0.0969988452825	0.853281595094
37	0.139768253701	0.874010778291	76	0.0947321058373	0.824718927024
38	0.13162425239	0.796073959391	77	0.0943957618124	0.82964767976
39	0.129882647187	0.795545193971	78	0.0938519241715	0.830766452982
40	0.129711778826	0.813798355495	79	0.0937509513048	0.839607760498

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0937509513048	0.850235706833	121	0.0763242362643	0.852331013125
81	0.0919528195156	0.828157817779	122	0.0761763789807	0.856048688978
82	0.0915710548522	0.831434943005	123	0.0761433721607	0.862317720178
83	0.0910317249973	0.831690275451	124	0.076036054451	0.866879668907
84	0.0909144184985	0.839542725467	125	0.0760184592503	0.873466242923
85	0.0909144184985	0.849537281723	126	0.0760184541702	0.880453855191
86	0.0900588386348	0.843430150423	127	0.0760184541702	0.887441584201
87	0.0898257214237	0.848825986059	128	0.0738150375919	0.843330187542
88	0.0896744760851	0.855693739323	129	0.073550686212	0.843842033126
89	0.0896488657968	0.864923290229	130	0.073243451933	0.843293877065
90	0.0896483053543	0.874630593785	131	0.0730217211367	0.844643437662
91	0.0896483053543	0.884348711494	132	0.0729426519813	0.849248943702
92	0.086570142383	0.833723565648	133	0.0729426519813	0.855682647821
93	0.0862263414641	0.836105064489	134	0.0720703840698	0.841620794914
94	0.0855553409429	0.831993804927	135	0.0717907107544	0.841333652939
95	0.0854014716287	0.837823042478	136	0.0716893596772	0.845174328633
96	0.0854014716287	0.846642232399	137	0.0714507160354	0.845729976448
97	0.084100942843	0.829605169913	138	0.0713697966943	0.849974686377
98	0.0837772217886	0.831717750804	139	0.0713681970154	0.856095544982
99	0.083455964247	0.833773215465	140	0.0709353618023	0.851827385812
100	0.0832701007771	0.838448065031	141	0.070381230505	0.844560586181
101	0.0832511686235	0.846447520537	142	0.0701800157823	0.845694008503
102	0.0826383405435	0.84228939594	143	0.0701223858095	0.850251470148
103	0.0817951766116	0.833279312542	144	0.069981022091	0.852748650365
104	0.0816036793814	0.837434420196	145	0.0698954639289	0.856572193923
105	0.0813941071515	0.841149541373	146	0.0698841268503	0.862199821828
106	0.0812746043098	0.846668844702	147	0.0698841268503	0.86810530006
107	0.0812387210202	0.853901780122	148	0.0687730417289	0.846439978715
108	0.0812387210202	0.86188217059	149	0.0685673163387	0.847068551919
109	0.0796676875182	0.836544227478	150	0.0685227377042	0.851645110834
110	0.0794062862748	0.83868802422	151	0.0682899770133	0.851508262889
111	0.0791189461985	0.840198599723	152	0.0681942024593	0.854744831657
112	0.0789788627914	0.844768596746	153	0.0681823213499	0.860068384395
113	0.0789480430295	0.851646111959	154	0.0681823213499	0.865689746384
114	0.0789480430295	0.859182803215	155	0.0673630255638	0.85049713383
115	0.0777353586447	0.840297438773	156	0.0670955227467	0.849199375987
116	0.0774183010809	0.840704261375	157	0.0670219662581	0.85277010722
117	0.0771628851418	0.842365872064	158	0.0668265258349	0.853203917026
118	0.0769804802157	0.845553760797	159	0.0666869201997	0.855020312633
119	0.0769268913166	0.85153266608	160	0.0666695316811	0.859949162393
120	0.0769268913166	0.85868840277	161	0.0666695316811	0.865323844658

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexagon for $162 \leq N \leq 243$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.066215008308	0.858866921464	203	0.0591010018215	0.857400454789
163	0.0661578166579	0.862676403419	204	0.0589654875339	0.857677349875
164	0.0660802362181	0.865934430312	205	0.0588658764442	0.858972136663
165	0.0660043589116	0.869214905053	206	0.0588312738187	0.862147772316
166	0.0659883799472	0.874059519124	207	0.058825759948	0.866170571837
167	0.0659861273713	0.879264905759	208	0.058825759948	0.870354970735
168	0.0659861273713	0.884529965075	209	0.0584778754629	0.86422623221
169	0.0659861273713	0.889795024391	210	0.0584270098472	0.866851295343
170	0.064423117198	0.853159787651	211	0.0583762994407	0.869467921296
171	0.0641824137713	0.851777548711	212	0.0583556172646	0.872969723465
172	0.0641133150727	0.854914926515	213	0.058303398214	0.875518498228
173	0.0638770629978	0.853559830344	214	0.0582948291015	0.879370366682
174	0.0636844980527	0.853325442953	215	0.0582930607132	0.883425973665
175	0.0636561545288	0.857465852091	216	0.0582930607132	0.887534931682
176	0.0636561545288	0.86236565696	217	0.0582930607132	0.891643889699
177	0.0630227925715	0.850093193274	218	0.0570725457381	0.858635755521
178	0.0628723454543	0.850819260303	219	0.0569750469225	0.859629843131
179	0.0627490544154	0.852246818463	220	0.0568266748204	0.859063279713
180	0.0625656517146	0.852005575687	221	0.0566735592532	0.858323961452
181	0.0624799758242	0.854394151375	222	0.0565344083097	0.857979009845
182	0.0624537787687	0.858394280569	223	0.0564758711306	0.860059953755
183	0.0624537709555	0.863110516704	224	0.0564671866148	0.863651049565
184	0.0621332891829	0.85894330449	225	0.0564671866148	0.867506634607
185	0.061707278558	0.851809543391	226	0.0559755594067	0.856255374461
186	0.0616044571534	0.853562251883	227	0.0558615210632	0.856543369352
187	0.0615038485071	0.855350624228	228	0.0557539275747	0.857005810513
188	0.0614235721473	0.857681366329	229	0.0557144809788	0.859547035514
189	0.0613497630924	0.860172532776	230	0.0555968651474	0.859659429152
190	0.0613199603518	0.86388377617	231	0.0555369535729	0.861537275873
191	0.061314330017	0.868271063438	232	0.055519025901	0.864708337643
192	0.061314330017	0.872816985236	233	0.055519025901	0.868435528753
193	0.060467521196	0.853295835982	234	0.0552727934508	0.864443617068
194	0.0603829277573	0.85531886199	235	0.0549348524196	0.857554584114
195	0.0602638571961	0.856340429207	236	0.0548519266795	0.858605691282
196	0.0601183008036	0.856579056915	237	0.054795474358	0.860469961828
197	0.0600417318089	0.858757677972	238	0.0547621698122	0.863050559778
198	0.0600053673462	0.862071671762	239	0.054684221648	0.864211332747
199	0.060000389653	0.866281827893	240	0.0546435849077	0.866537965664
200	0.060000389653	0.870635002908	241	0.0546169892631	0.869301724574
201	0.0593901870743	0.857281457404	242	0.0546167510236	0.872901170424
202	0.0592562142057	0.857663955982	243	0.0546167510236	0.876508200054

Table 4: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexagon for $244 \leq N \leq 325$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
244	0.0539850542351	0.859874156923	285	0.0500699055858	0.863965481542
245	0.0538906828592	0.860382253583	286	0.0499820851885	0.863958258085
246	0.0537914625657	0.860715846591	287	0.0499780817565	0.86684021128
247	0.0537816689305	0.863900030673	288	0.049970409032	0.869593495851
248	0.053638176698	0.862775254236	289	0.0499704090341	0.872612917786
249	0.0536046934711	0.865173018998	290	0.0497755645601	0.868817126372
250	0.0535727183166	0.867611623376	291	0.0495595165153	0.864261360758
251	0.0535717392002	0.871050229675	292	0.0494462966075	0.863273435513
252	0.0535717392002	0.874520549315	293	0.0493909707172	0.864292471677
253	0.0531023162936	0.862671474745	294	0.0493569508673	0.866047996673
254	0.0529828294069	0.862188045115	295	0.0493093589087	0.867318708637
255	0.0528839209223	0.862353759447	296	0.0492863396027	0.869446428216
256	0.0528527778762	0.864716185471	297	0.0492519731245	0.871167576389
257	0.0527247563857	0.86389363284	298	0.0492382811399	0.873614870329
258	0.052665083928	0.865293125692	299	0.0492382811399	0.876546463853
259	0.0526372848199	0.867730191591	300	0.0492382811399	0.879478057378
260	0.052633364605	0.870950756845	301	0.0487270748406	0.864181895191
261	0.052633364605	0.874300567448	302	0.0486496760559	0.864300640386
262	0.0523522106786	0.868299054947	303	0.0485769523366	0.864571953724
263	0.0523161926249	0.870414255217	304	0.0485585492875	0.866768214592
264	0.0522809517279	0.872547107151	305	0.0484641829188	0.866242756213
265	0.0522566755194	0.875039009854	306	0.0484415450327	0.868271179229
266	0.0522179134745	0.877038486141	307	0.0483986991972	0.869568382569
267	0.0522147993773	0.880230626045	308	0.0483873587373	0.871992070484
268	0.0522065753567	0.883249074339	309	0.0483873501903	0.874822904518
269	0.0522065065959	0.886542444524	310	0.0483873501903	0.877654046604
270	0.0522065065959	0.889838141344	311	0.0480099461458	0.866803812688
271	0.0522065065959	0.893133838162	312	0.0479155506687	0.8661748062
272	0.0512779137054	0.864823703821	313	0.0478374501001	0.866120600353
273	0.0511494079395	0.863658109851	314	0.0478002055889	0.86753531624
274	0.0510424715812	0.863201011145	315	0.0477128209987	0.867119054302
275	0.0510272185197	0.86583367225	316	0.0477005525792	0.869424529643
276	0.0508774593031	0.863888911213	317	0.0476313799919	0.869648149008
277	0.0507825810512	0.863788257813	318	0.0476222847072	0.872058381392
278	0.050741980539	0.86552100291	319	0.0476205093431	0.874735479226
279	0.0507372114413	0.868471114422	320	0.0476205093431	0.877477596716
280	0.0507372114413	0.871583914115	321	0.0473915932115	0.871777461541
281	0.050354694958	0.861557455604	322	0.047358595522	0.873275923534
282	0.0502564442357	0.861252727982	323	0.0473588628604	0.875997850464
283	0.0501803949722	0.861693014961	324	0.0473119460071	0.876969763005
284	0.0501592674772	0.864009857234	325	0.0473119460084	0.879676459852

Table 5: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hexagon for $362 \leq N \leq 400$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
326	0.0472721173962	0.880898148874	364	0.0444217088077	0.868540134743
327	0.0472725827542	0.883617687264	365	0.0443644282993	0.868681613767
328	0.0472708283684	0.886254096826	366	0.044324330631	0.869487700966
329	0.0472708180475	0.888955702845	367	0.0442616191075	0.869398013681
330	0.0472708180475	0.891657695863	368	0.0442601335359	0.871708427611
331	0.0472708180475	0.894359688881	369	0.0441562629177	0.869979408801
332	0.0465082240205	0.86835154512	370	0.0441387269935	0.871644345882
333	0.0464138248414	0.867434992532	371	0.0441207865171	0.873289799571
334	0.0463380244264	0.867200423731	372	0.0441178577273	0.875527431772
335	0.0463019031077	0.868441316343	373	0.0441178577273	0.877881000136
336	0.0461832822622	0.866576393006	374	0.0441178577273	0.880234568501
337	0.0461785587567	0.868977708598	375	0.0438161089293	0.870556312958
338	0.0460849006446	0.868024528554	376	0.0437715440063	0.871103109001
339	0.046063181425	0.869772243642	377	0.043714189828	0.871132475112
340	0.0460629955515	0.872330903398	378	0.0436291011155	0.870046204629
341	0.0460629955515	0.874896582526	379	0.0436197508221	0.871974042842
342	0.045747317864	0.865476670789	380	0.0435523237627	0.871573961188
343	0.0456995025607	0.866193762272	381	0.0434952051729	0.871576936635
344	0.045627383023	0.865979376973	382	0.0434893811907	0.873630535924
345	0.0455861321614	0.866927085482	383	0.0434794786316	0.875518678339
346	0.045560875522	0.868476771751	384	0.0434794794303	0.877804660139
347	0.0454797417128	0.867887513766	385	0.0434794794303	0.880090609775
348	0.0454413651052	0.868920351729	386	0.0433080896337	0.875433869343
349	0.0454303318452	0.870994136745	387	0.0432853045512	0.87677852958
350	0.045430088795	0.873480475714	388	0.0432445805677	0.877390828394
351	0.045430088795	0.875976134217	389	0.0432251734349	0.878862788466
352	0.0452691075174	0.872257102888	390	0.0432221019875	0.880996860656
353	0.0450467025922	0.866161157454	391	0.0431949426777	0.882146159427
354	0.0450272536175	0.867864982409	392	0.0431903194404	0.884212979308
355	0.044979011597	0.868452669989	393	0.0431877751264	0.886364185144
356	0.0449419068274	0.869462737707	394	0.04318777455	0.88861954103
357	0.0449220533555	0.871134875888	395	0.0431877751277	0.890874944407
358	0.0448773287624	0.871836425263	396	0.0431877751276	0.893130324012
359	0.0448445669502	0.872995698686	397	0.0431877751277	0.89538570362
360	0.0448350602096	0.875056311695	398	0.042574353312	0.87232270833
361	0.0448241729341	0.877060915936	399	0.0425107895596	0.871905113085
362	0.0448241526771	0.879489652639	400	0.0424600625767	0.872005526518
363	0.0448241526771	0.881919182066			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($194 \leq N \leq 205$).

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($206 \leq N \leq 217$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($218 \leq N \leq 229$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($230 \leq N \leq 241$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($242 \leq N \leq 253$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($254 \leq N \leq 265$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($266 \leq N \leq 277$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($278 \leq N \leq 289$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($290 \leq N \leq 301$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($302 \leq N \leq 313$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($314 \leq N \leq 325$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($326 \leq N \leq 337$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($338 \leq N \leq 349$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($350 \leq N \leq 361$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($362 \leq N \leq 373$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($374 \leq N \leq 385$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($386 \leq N \leq 397$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($398 \leq N \leq 400$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of a pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 35: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 36: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 37: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 38: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 39: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 40: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 41: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 42: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 43: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 44: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 45: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 46: Best packing for N equal circles inside a equilateral triangle ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 47: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 48: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 49: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 50: Best packing for N equal circles inside an equilateral triangle ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 51: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($194 \leq N \leq 205$).

Figure 52: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($206 \leq N \leq 217$).

Figure 53: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($218 \leq N \leq 229$).

Figure 54: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($230 \leq N \leq 241$).

Figure 55: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($242 \leq N \leq 253$).

Figure 56: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($254 \leq N \leq 265$).

Figure 57: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($266 \leq N \leq 277$).

Figure 58: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($278 \leq N \leq 289$).

Figure 59: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($290 \leq N \leq 301$).

Figure 60: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($302 \leq N \leq 313$).

Figure 61: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($314 \leq N \leq 325$).

Figure 62: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($326 \leq N \leq 337$).

Figure 63: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($338 \leq N \leq 349$).

Figure 64: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($349 \leq N \leq 360$).

Figure 65: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($361 \leq N \leq 372$).

Figure 66: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($373 \leq N \leq 384$).

Figure 67: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($385 \leq N \leq 396$).

Figure 68: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hexagon ($397 \leq N \leq 400$).

References

- [1] Amore, Paolo. "Circle packing in regular polygons." arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.12287 (2022).
- [2] Paolo Amore, "Coordinates of the packing configurations of arXiv:2212.12287 ", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574070>